

Thus as the iodide concentration rises there is reached a point when production of this state is inhibited and the iodine concentration no longer increases. Iodine, iodide and tri-iodide ions are now present and subject to at least four possible fates.

The principal consumption of iodine is via iodination of the organic species which is also the principal source of iodide ion. In the oscillatory system the iodination reaction together with the reoxidation of iodide produced maintains a steady state iodide concentration until the iodine concentration decreases appreciably. Eventually the iodide concentration decreases to a point where the production of the state responsible for production of iodine via the Mn(II) catalysed reaction is no longer inhibited, the remaining iodide is rapidly removed and the cycle commenced again. Thus the reaction can be regarded as a series of autocatalytic reaction 'bursts' occurring with a certain frequency.

We have to wait for sometime, however, for further elucidation of the mechanisms of these novel reactions.

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pH-Metric Studies of Schiff Base Complexes of Lanthanons

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THE complexes of Pr(III), Nd(III), Gd(III) and Dy(III) with N-4-methylphenacylidene-O-aminophenol (MPAP) have been investigated by pH-metric titration technique as employed by Calvin and Melchior¹. The protonation constant of the ligand and the stepwise formation constants of the metal chelates have been evaluated at constant ionic strength 0.25M NaClO₄ and temperature 30 ± 1°.

Experimental

The ligand (MPAP) has been prepared and characterised by a similar method as reported earlier². Lanthanon/chlorides or nitrates (B.D.H) were dissolved in double distilled water. The solutions were estimated gravimetrically by precipitating the metal oxalates and subsequent ignition and weighing as metal oxides. The solutions of required strength were then prepared by suitable dilution. Potassium hydroxide (B. D. H.) was washed by methanol two or three times in order to ensure the removal of carbonate, if any and then dissolved in methanol to obtain stock solution and its strength was determined by using standard oxalic acid solution.

Conditions of Study :

The pH-metric titrations were carried out at 30 ± 1° with a Philips PP 9040 pH-meter as recommended by Zeidler³ and Fritz⁴.

The instrument was standardised against 0.05M solution of potassiumhydrogenphthalate. The volume of the solutions to be titrated was always kept constant (20 ml) by mixing with necessary volume of methanol. The following three mixtures (a), (b) & (c) were prepared for each system and titrated against standard alkali.

- (a) 10.0 ml of ligand (0.025M) + 5.0 ml of 1M NaClO₄
- (b) 10 ml of ligand (0.025M) + 5.0 ml of 1M NaClO₄ + 1.0 ml of metal salt solution (0.005 M).
- (c) 10.0 ml of ligand (0.025 M) + 5.0 ml of 1M NaClO₄ + 2.0 ml of metal salt solution (0.005 M).

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TABLE 1—*pK* VALUE OF LIGAND (MPAP) IN METHANOL

Vol. of KOH (0.1M) in ml.	0.0	0.25	0.50	0.75	1.00	1.25	1.50	1.75	2.00	2.25
<i>pH</i>	5.20	5.85	6.50	6.75	6.85	7.00	7.20	7.30	7.35	7.40
<i>nH</i>	1.00	0.90	0.80	0.70	0.60	0.50	0.40	0.30	0.20	0.10

pK value from Fig. No. 1 = $1.0 \times 10^{-7.0}$.

Results and Discussions

The protonation constant is determined by plotting *pH* values of the solution resulting from progressive addition of standard alkali to ligand solution of known strength vs *nH* values (where *nH*=average number of protons associated with a ligand).

$$nH = \frac{\text{Total number of H}^+ \text{ bound to R}}{\text{Total number of ligand mole present}}$$

$$\therefore nH = \frac{[RH]}{[R^-][H^+]} = \frac{R^- - P - H^+ + GH^-}{R^-}$$

where R^- = Total concentration of the ligand,
 P = The concentration of alkali added.

The correct value of *pK* is obtained from Fig. No.1 as *pH* where *nH* = 0.5

present in the system. Titrations of the ligand with and without metal ion are performed against KOH. The curves are drawn between *pH* vs volume of alkali added. The horizontal distance between the two curves at any value of *pH* gives the amount of proton liberated by chelation i.e., the amount of ligand complexed. This value divided by the total amount of metal ion in the system gave \bar{n} . Thus at various values of *pH* a set of \bar{n} values is determined. The values of \bar{n} were plotted against the corresponding values of $-\log L$. The final values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$, as shown in Table 2 are equal to the values of $-\log L$ at $\bar{n} = 0.5$ and 1.5 respectively.

The calculations were made by taking 1.0×10^{-7} as dissociation constant of the ligand. The gradual increase in the value of \bar{n} with the increase of *pH*

TABLE 2—METAL-LIGAND APPARENT STABILITY CONSTANTS OF THE CHELATES, $\mu = 0.25M(\text{NaClO}_4)$, TEMP. $30 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$

System	Fig. No.	Curve No.	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log \beta$
$\text{Pr}^{3+} \pm \text{MPAP}$	2	I	2.875	0.55	3.425
		II	2.25	0.05	2.30
$\text{Nd}^{3+} \pm \text{MPAP}$	3	I	2.80	0.60	3.40
		II	2.15	0.05	2.20
$\text{Gd}^{3+} \pm \text{MPAP}$	4	I	2.65	0.50	3.15
		II	2.10	0.05	2.15
$\text{Dy}^{3+} \pm \text{MPAP}$	5	I	2.10	0.60	2.70
		II	1.95	0.05	2.00

In order to determine the stepwise formation constants of a chelate, Bjerrum⁵, introduced the concept of degree of formation defined as the average number of ligands (\bar{n}) bound per metal ion

showed that the anionic form of the ligand was responsible for the complex ion formation with Pr(III) , Nd(III) , Gd(III) and Dy(III) . The complexation reaction is as follows :

Studies on Stable Ylids : Synthesis of 9-Arylidene 2, 7-Dibromofluorenes Via 2, 7-Dibromofluorenylidetriphenylphosphorane

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THE reactions of fluorenylidetriphenylphosphorane have been extensively studied with substituted benzaldehydes yielding benzalfluorenes as Wittig products¹⁻². But the effect of substituents which could enhance the reactivity of such ylid has not been examined. Although the stabilized ylid, 2, 7-dibromofluorenylidetriphenylphosphorane, was synthesized in 1962 by Schoenberg *et al.*,³ yet its synthetic utility has not been investigated so far. Continuing our researches into the reactivity and synthetic utility of the ylids⁴⁻¹¹, we now wish to report the effect of bromine atom on the reactivity of 2, 7-dibromofluorenylidetriphenylphosphorane with substituted aromatic aldehydes.

Treatment of the salt-2, 7-dibromofluorenyltriphenylphosphonium bromide (1), prepared by the quaternization of triphenylphosphine with 2, 7, 9-tribromofluorene, with 30% NH_4OH in boiling ethanol gave ylid-2, 9-dibromofluorenylidetriphenylphosphorane (2) which on subsequent reaction with a series of aromatic aldehydes afforded 9-arylidene-2, 7-dibromofluorenes (3a-j) in 50-90% yields. Ylid (2), however, failed to undergo reaction with aromatic ketones even after prolonged refluxing. The Ylide (2) was found to be more nucleophilic than fluorenylidetriphenylphosphorane¹ since former coupled quickly with the aldehydes and yielded products (3a-j) in better yields. One of the most plausible reasons to the enhanced nucleophilicity is the +M effect exerted by the bromine atoms on the fluorene nucleus.

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The fluorene derivatives (3a-j) gave satisfactory elemental analyses and melting points for known compounds and were in accordance with that reported in literature¹¹⁻¹². The IR spectra of 3a-j showed absorption bands at $1600-1585\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\nu\text{C}=\text{C}$) and $970-940\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The latter absorptions are associated